

LOGITRONICS

A Nearly Forgotten Antecedent of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

This essay analyzes and historically contextualizes a set of handwritten notes entitled Logitronics, prepared by the author around 1980 during a self-taught learning process in digital logic and automation. Based on the rediscovery of these materials, a reflection is proposed on conceptual foundations that, decades before the contemporary rise of artificial intelligence, already introduced essential principles such as binary numeration, Boolean algebra, and their correspondence with electrical circuits. The work integrates a brief interpreted reconstruction of the original content, accompanied by images of the notes, in order to highlight their historical and didactic value. These concepts are also linked to the subsequent development of modern computing, showing how elementary logical operations constitute the basis for the functioning of current artificial intelligence systems. Finally, the essay presents a personal reflection on the conceptual transition from the initial fascination with machines that “moved by themselves” to the current technological aspiration to create machines capable of learning, reasoning, and eventually feeling.

Keywords: Logitronics; digital logic; Boolean algebra; automation; artificial Intelligence

Introduction

Today, the development of artificial intelligence occupies a central place as a new global scientific and technological paradigm. However, it is important to recognize that behind this sophisticated technology lie simple conceptual principles such as the binary representation of information and the logical operations formalized by George Boole in the nineteenth century. The masterful combination of those principles and operations, now perceived as “elementary,” received during the early emergence of AI the name Logitronics, a term that today is curiously flagged as a “linguistic error” in Word and other writing software. The term was abandoned when artificial intelligence began to acquire a clearly defined identity. The notes presented here correspond to a self-directed learning process initiated around 1980, when the author consulted various technical texts of the time related to digital logic, as well as introductory works on “Logitronics.” It should be emphasized that these notes do not constitute a photocopy or literal reproduction of any specific source, but rather a didactic reinterpretation of the information consulted.

An Early Encounter with Automation

My interest in technological automation began during my adolescence. I was fascinated by observing how certain devices were capable of executing various actions on their own, without visible human intervention. My most memorable experiences in this regard took place during visits to the Pacific International Fair in Lima, where large factories from different countries exhibited machines and devices in full operation, displaying technological ingenuity capable of capturing the attention of even the most indifferent visitor. Metal arms moved to perform complex assembly tasks, doors opened and closed with astonishing precision, and pieces aligned one after another like soldiers in perfect formation before being labeled. I remember that visiting the Italian and German pavilions was essential for me. Their products did not feature flashy lights, loud sounds, or colorful gifts for children, but rather heavy machine tools that dazzled through silent, precise processes, of particular interest to those involved in industrial manufacturing. The star of the German pavilion was Siemens, which exhibited enormous and elegant automated machines of extremely high precision that ultimately left me with the same recurring question: “How do they do it?” Later I learned that this German company was a pioneer in industrial automation, electrical control, and ingenious design of logical industrial systems.

Interpreted and Organized Transcription of the Logitronics Notes

The following notes provide a clear and structured introduction to the fundamentals of logical systems used in electrical and electronic circuits.

LOGITRONICS

Introduction

A large number of automated processes or systems are based on logical systems, which may belong to different technologies: electrical, electronic, hydraulic, pneumatic, or hybrid. These systems are called logical because their operating principles are based on actions derived from logical philosophy. The mathematical principles of logic were initiated by George Boole (1815–1864), an English philosopher and mathematician who gave scientific momentum to the laws of logical reasoning through what is now known as Boolean algebra.

THEORY

Binary Numeration

In everyday life we perform calculations using the decimal system, which employs ten digits:

0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9.

However, some mechanical devices use other numbering systems, such as:

- odometers
- revolution counters
- stepped counters

Unlike these mechanical systems, logical circuits are not mechanical in nature but electrical, magnetic, or electronic. Consequently, the components used in these circuits can possess only two differentiated states.

These states may be represented in various ways:

Device	State 0	State 1
Contact	deactivated	activated
Lamp	off	on
Line	no voltage	with voltage
Relay	inactive	active
Diode	infinite resistance	zero resistance
Transistor	blocked	conducting

Because of this, logical circuits use binary numeration, which employs only the digits 0 and 1. This corresponds to a base-2 numbering system. Any number expressed in base 10 can also be represented in base 2.

Comparative table

Decimal	Binary
0	0
1	1
2	10
3	11
4	100
5	101
6	110
7	111
8	1000
9	1001

Binary operations

In Logitronics there are three fundamental Boolean algebra operations:

- sum
- product
- inversion

1. SUM (OR logic)

The sum between two binary values is:

A	B	A + B
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

The logical sum equals 1 when at least one operand is 1.

2. PRODUCT (AND logic)

A	B	A · B
0	0	0
0	1	0
1	0	0
1	1	1

The logical product equals 1 only when both factors are 1.

3. INVERSION (NOT logic)

Inversion consists of negating the given constant.

A	\tilde{A}
0	1
1	0

The bar over the binary constant indicates inversion. The apostrophe may also be used. Double inversion returns the original value.

Binary variables

Logical circuits are composed of elements capable of adopting two states. By convention, these two states are assigned the values 0 and 1.

For example:

Device	State 1	State 0
Contact	activated	deactivated
Lamp	on	off
Line	with voltage	no voltage
Relay	active	inactive

Contacts or logical devices constitute the variables of the logical circuit, since they can assume either of the two binary values. In logical equations these variables are represented by uppercase letters.

Parallel circuit (OR)

Consider two contacts A and B connected in parallel with a lamp L.

The lamp turns on if:

- A is closed
- B is closed
- both are closed

Equation: $L = A + B$

This circuit corresponds to the OR gate.

Series Circuit (AND)

Two contacts in series require both to be closed:

- $A = 1$
- $B = 1$

Equation: $L = A \cdot B$

This circuit corresponds to the AND gate.

Inversion Circuit (NOT)

A normally closed contact produces inversion:

Equation: $L = \bar{A}$

This circuit corresponds to the NOT gate.

Boolean Rules

(only the title appears in the notes, without further explanation)

My original notes on Logitronics (circa 1980)

The original pages are reproduced below.

Picture 1

Picture 2

« Tabla Comparativa »

DECIMAL	BINARIA
0	0
1	1
2	10
3	11
4	100
5	101
6	110
7	111
8	1000
9	1001

« Operaciones Binarias »

En Logitrónica existen 3 operaciones algebraicas booleanas fundamentales:

- SUMA
- PRODUCTO
- INVERSION

SUMA: La suma entre 2 valores binarios 0, 1 (o constantes binarias), se establece:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 + 0 &= 0 \\ 0 + 1 &= 1 \\ 1 + 0 &= 1 \\ 1 + 1 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

La suma lógica es 1, cuando por lo menos uno de los sumandos es 1.

PRODUCTO: Se establece:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \cdot 0 &= 0 \\ 0 \cdot 1 &= 0 \\ 1 \cdot 0 &= 0 \\ 1 \cdot 1 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

El producto es 1 sólo si ambos factores son 1.

Picture 3

INVERSION: Es la negación de la constante dada.

Así;

$$\bar{0} = 1$$

$$\bar{1} = 0$$

(La barra sobre la constante binaria indica inversión. Puede usarse también el apóstrofe '0', '1'.)

Existe también la **DOBLE INVERSION** que da como resultado la misma constante.

Así;

$$\bar{\bar{0}} = 0$$

$$\bar{\bar{1}} = 1$$

Como se observará, estas operaciones lógicas se apartan del Algebra Clásica.

Variables Binarias.

Como se ha dicho, los circuitos lógicos están constituidos por órganos que pueden poseer 2 únicos estados. Por convencionalismo, a estas 2 constantes binarias se les atribuyen las siguientes condiciones:

ORGANOS	ESTADOS	BINARIOS
	<u>1</u>	<u>0</u>
DE CONTACTO	ACCIONADO	DESACCIONADO
LÁMPARA	ENCENDIDA	APAGADA
LÍNEA	CON TENSIÓN	SIN TENSIÓN
RELÉ	ACTIVADO	DESACTIVADO

Se puede ver que cuando un contacto está desaccionado, posee el estado cero, y cuando está accionado posee el estado uno.

Los contactos, o cualquier clase de órgano lógico, constituyen las variables del circuito lógico, puesto que pueden tomar una de las 2 constantes binarias.

Todos los órganos representados en esquemas o ecuaciones lógicas, se simbolizan por medio de letras mayúsculas. Los contactos, ya sea en trabajo o en reposo, se representan así:

TRABAJO

REPOSO

* Norma Americana

Picture 4

« CIRCUITO Paralelo »

Considérese el circuito #1, sea 2 contactos de trabajo en paralelo, y a la vez en serie, conectados a una lámpara:

Para que la lámpara L se halle en el estado 1 (encendida), es necesario que el contacto A, el contacto B, o ambos tengan el valor 1 (que estén cerrados). Estas condiciones constituyen así, las mismas características de la suma lógica.

Para apreciar mejor la similitud del circuito paralelo con la suma lógica veamos este cuadro de valores:

A	B	A + B
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

$$L = A + B \quad *$$

* El valor de L (lámpara) corresponderá a la suma lógica de A y B. De manera general, el circuito paralelo quedará establecido por la ecuación: $A + B + C \dots X + Y + Z = L$

Al circuito paralelo se le conoce comúnmente por reunión o puerta O (OR (INGLÉS) OU (FRANCÉS)).

De manera gráfica, a la puerta O; se la representa mediante este símbolo:

A, B, C, son las variables de entrada de la puerta, y la suma lógica

Picture 5

(punto 5) constituyen la salida.
 = Representación Gráfica de las 8 posibles combinaciones para una Puerta O, de 3 entradas =

El número posible es 2^n (n = número de entradas de la puerta)

« Circuito Serie »

Considerese el circuito #2, o sea dos contactos en serie con una lámpara:

Para que la lámpara L se halle en el estado 1, es necesario que los contactos A y B estén AMBOS en el valor 1. Estas condiciones constituyen así los mismos características del producto lógico.

Para apreciar mejor dicha equivalencia, veamos este cuadro de valores:

A	B	A · B
0	0	0
0	1	0
1	0	0
1	1	1

$L = A \cdot B$

Ecuación: $A \cdot B \cdot C \dots X \cdot Y \cdot Z = L$

El circuito serie se le conoce por intersección o puerta Y (AND, ET).

Representación Gráfica:

Picture 6

PUERTA Y

Possible combinations of a 3-input AND gate:

« Circuito de Inversión »

Consider the circuit #3, formed by a contact at rest, in series with a lamp:

For the case where the contact is not actuated (0), the lamp L will remain lit (1), and vice versa, if it is actuated (1) the lamp will remain unlit (0). These specifications constitute the conditions of the inversion operation.

Equation: $\bar{A} = L$

Truth Table:

\bar{A}	L
0	1
1	0

The inversion circuit is also known as negation, or NOT gate.
 Graphical representation of the NOT gate:

Picture 7

Conclusion

The publication of these old notes written with a ballpoint pen makes it possible to understand how many fundamental concepts of modern computing were already part of technical learning decades before the contemporary rise of artificial intelligence. What in the last century was for me an early and persistent curiosity about the hidden secret behind automated systems eventually became a first approach to the deepest foundations of artificial intelligence, which today operates at high speed on millions of Boolean logic circuits.

Approximately forty years ago, my passion was to open the chest that held the secrets allowing machines to move by themselves. Today, the scientific and technological world works tirelessly to make machines think by themselves. Tomorrow, the task might be to create machines capable of feeling.